

q-Gaussians and SERS Bands of L-Cysteine

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Abstract: Here we start considering the q-Gaussian Tsallis functions, previously studied in fitting Raman bands, for being applied to SERS bands. The case study here proposed is that of L-Cysteine.

Keywords: Tsallis q-Gaussian distribution, Gaussian distribution, Cauchy distribution, Lorentzian distribution, Raman spectroscopy, SERS, L-cysteine.

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q-Gaussian Tsallis functions are probability distributions based on a generalized form of the exponential function, characterized by a continuous parameter q (Tsallis, 1988, 1995, Umarov et al., 2008, Hanel et al., 2009, Sparavigna, 2022). The q-Gaussian function is given as $f(x) = C e_q(-\beta x^2)$, where $e_q(\cdot)$ is the q-exponential function and C a constant. We assume the exponent as $\beta = 1/(2\sigma^2)$, with variance σ . The q-exponential has expression: $exp_q(u) = [1 + (1 - q)u]^{1/(1-q)}$. In the range $1 < q < 2$, the shape of q-Gaussian function is intermediate between the Gaussian and the Lorentzian profile. For q equal to 2, the q-Gaussian is the Cauchy-Lorentzian distribution (Naudts, 2009). When q is close to 1, we have the usual Gaussian form (if $q=1.01$ the q-Gaussian and the Gaussian are numerically indistinguishable).

The q-Gaussian behavior turns the function into line-shape suitable for the analysis of Raman spectroscopy, where the spectral bands are characterized by intermediate profiles between Lorentzian and Gaussian outlines (Kirillov, 2004). Besides these two functions most popularly used for fitting Raman spectra, *linear combinations* (pseudo-Voigt distributions) or *convolutions* of them (Voigt distributions) are used too (Meier, 2005). Of the reason for using Voigtian functions, and consequently their pseudo-Voigtian approximations, we discussed in the previous works about q-Gaussians fitting onto graphite and anatase TiO_2 Raman bands ([ChemRxiv1](#), [ChemRxiv2](#)). We have also shown that the q-Gaussian is able of mimicking, besides Voigt and pseudo-Voigt, the Egelstaff-Schofield line shape. A detailed discussion of the decomposition by means of q-Gaussians of Raman bands for carbonaceous material has been also proposed (available [link](#)).

Several successful examples show that the intermediate shape of q-Gaussians is properly fitting onto Raman data. Here we start investigating the following problem: can we use q-Gaussians also for SERS spectra? In Camerlingo et al., 2022, we can find Lorentzian functions applied to SERS fitting (Camerlingo and coworkers used Gaussian-Lorentzian curves "to analyze the infrared spectra, while only Lorentzian functions were used for Raman and SERS spectra"). Being a q-Gaussian a Lorentzian function when $q=2$, we can approach the SERS q-Gaussian fitting for sure.

SERS means Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy. It is a Raman spectroscopy based on the photons scattering by molecules adsorbed on rough metal surfaces or nanostructures. It was fifty years ago that the first SERS spectrum has been observed by Martin Fleischmann, Patrick J. Hendra and A. James McQuillan,

at the University of Southampton. The spectrum was that of pyridine adsorbed on roughened silver surface. In 1977, two research groups published different mechanisms for the signal enhancement: David L. Jeanmaire and Richard Van Duyne proposed the origin in an electromagnetic effect, whereas M. Grant Albrecht and J. Alan Creighton proposed a charge-transfer effect.

To answer the question about the use of q-Gaussians for SERS spectra, we start considering the spectrum of L-Cysteine as proposed by Sherman et al., 2020, in their “A surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy database of 63 metabolites”.

In the following plots, data are generally given in red and the best fits in green: q-Gaussian components are shown in blue and magenta colours. The misfit is also proposed in the lower part of the images. Data and best fits are given as functions of integers n (equally spaced points), for the x-axis, which is representing the Raman shift. A convenient scale is used for the y-axis (intensity axis). Semi log plots are also proposed.

Fig. 1: SERS data of L-Cysteine (data courtesy Sherman et al., 2020). On the right, the data with log scale y-axis (semi log scale). The semi log scale helps us to identify several band ranges. The endpoints of frequency ranges are easily determined by their lowest intensities. Negative data are not represented in the semi log scale.

In Brolo et al., 2002, we can find a study of the adsorption of L-cysteine on a polycrystalline silver electrode. The methods of investigation are the surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) and surface-enhanced second harmonic generation (SESHG), defined as “in situ spectroelectrochemical methods”.

In the Fig.4 of Brolo and coworkers we can find the SERS spectra of L-Cys, which has been adsorbed on the surface of an electrochemically roughened silver electrode, from measurements at different applied potentials. “The band at ca. 665 cm^{-1} was predominant for potentials more positive than -600 mV (Figure 4a-c [of Brolo et al., 2022]). This band can be assigned to the C-S stretching mode. The frequency of this mode is red-shifted from around 690 cm^{-1} for L-Cys in solution”. “This shift indicates that the sulfur atom of L-Cys should be directly bonded to the surface” (Brolo et al., 2022). When the potential becomes “more negative than -600 mV ”, we can see new SERS bands. “The SERS intensity for the C-S stretching mode does not change significantly as the potential becomes negative, indicating that L-Cys does not leave the Ag surface in the potential range studied. ... Moreover, all spectral features observed at potentials more negative than -600 mV (Figure 4d and e) can be assigned to L-Cys vibrations” (Brolo et al., 2002, see references therein). “The shoulder at 630 cm^{-1} and the peaks at 799 and 905 cm^{-1} can be related to the COO-wagging, the COO-bending, and the C-COO-stretching, respectively. All of the new SERS bands involved vibrational modes related to the carboxylate group” (Brolo et al., 2002).

As we can see from the Fig.1, the largest intensity is at 668.5 cm^{-1} (see Fig.2). Let us start with its range. In the following approach, the ranges will be fitted independently from each other.

Fig. 2: The best fit (green) onto data (red) of L-Cysteine (data courtesy Sherman et al., 2020). Frequency range from 583.3 to 766.5 cm^{-1} (see Fig.1). Three q -Gaussians are used (values of the q -parameters are given in the figure). The misfit is proposed in the lower part of the plot. On the right, the same fit is shown with the log scale for y -axis (semi log scale). Data and q -Gaussians are given as functions of integers n (equally spaced points used in fitting), for the x -axis which is representing the Raman shift. A convenient scale is used for the y -axis (intensity axis). The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=656$). The frequencies of the q -Gaussian centres are also given.

Chemical structure as given in Clemente Plaza et al., 2018.

In the Fig.2, we can see the main peak at 668.5 cm^{-1} . Thanks to the discussion by Brolo et al., 2022, we can link this peak to the C-S stretching mode. In the Figure 3 we can also see the shoulder at 630.8 cm^{-1} , related to the COO-wagging.

Fig. 3: Best fit (green) onto data (red) of L-Cysteine (data courtesy Sherman et al., 2020), frequency range from 768.8 to 857.8 cm^{-1} (see Fig.1). Three q -Gaussians are used. As in the previous case, the misfit is proposed in the lower part of the plot. On the right, the same fit is shown with the log scale for y-axis (semi log scale). Note the peak at 800 cm^{-1} , mentioned by Brolo et al., 2002, at 799 cm^{-1} . About the q -Gaussian component with $q=1.41$, that marked by the flash, see please the further discussion in the text and the Fig.5.

Fig. 4: The best fit (green) onto data (red) of L-Cysteine (Sherman et al., 2020). Frequency range from 860.0 to 1000.5 cm^{-1} (see Fig.1). Three q -Gaussians are used (values of the q -parameters are given in the figure). As in the previous cases, the misfit is proposed in the lower part of the plot. On the right, the same fit is shown with the log scale for y-axis (semi log scale).

As previously told, the frequency ranges are fitted independently from each other. But, in the Figure 3, the presence of the q -Gaussian component with $q=1.41$ (marked by a flash) is questionable, being the range influenced by the wing of the q -Gaussian with $q=1.19$ in the Figure 4. Let us remove the flashed component, and consider the presence of the first component of Fig.4. The best fit that we can obtain is given in the following Fig.5.

Fig.5: We can fit the range from 768.8 to 857.8 cm^{-1} with two q -Gaussians if we consider the left wing of $q=1.19$ q -Gaussian function.

Fig.6: The same as in the Figure 5, with semi log scale.

Fig. 7: The best fit (green) onto data (red) of L-Cysteine (Sherman et al., 2020). Frequency range from 1000.5 to 1174.8 cm^{-1} (see Fig.1). Three q -Gaussians are used (values of the q -parameters are given in the figure). On the right, the same fit is shown with the log scale for y-axis (semi log scale).

Fig. 8: q -Gaussian fit (green) onto data (red) of L-Cysteine (Sherman et al., 2020). Frequency range from 1255 to 1450.5 cm^{-1} (see Fig.1). Three q -Gaussians are used (values of the q -parameters are given in the figure). The fit could be improved by adding further q -Gaussian components.

Remarks

Tsallis q-Gaussians can be easily compared with Gaussian and Lorentzian functions, and with pseudo-Voigtian functions too. For q-parameter equal to 2, the q-Gaussian is the Lorentzian function, and for q close to 1 the Gaussian function. In the best fits of L-Cys data, we have found that the q-parameters are giving functions which have more Gaussian than Lorentzian character. Then, the pure Lorentzian functions used for SERS by Camerlingo et al., 2022, are not suitable for L-Cysteine data. Further studies are necessary, to understand the character of SERS line-shapes.

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